

RELEVANCE OF LEGAL ENGLISH AT PRESENT

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the relevance of English in modern jurisprudence, and the meaning and the role of learning English at present; high language proficiency and the perspectives of it for practicing lawyers.

Throughout this century, it has been witnessed that informational technologies have become the most influential in all areas of human life, with English becoming one of the main subjects of this process.

Almost every second person in the world speaks this language due to the fact that English has firmly established itself as a "world" language. It is irrefutable that English is the language of culture and art, music and poetry, travel and entertainment, and business and economics. Furthermore, the knowledge of English provides specific professional opportunities since being fluent in English can guarantee a highly-paid job nowadays. Indeed, knowledge of such an international language is one of the crucial components of modern world, equating to a successful future. Having analyzed the importance of the English language in jurisprudence the following points can be stated: this language is really vital for lawyers in the present realities of this world. In recent years, the legal business has been

developing significantly and has a strong place in the global economy. Thus, the need for international clients for law firms is increasing daily, which is why there is a great demand for legal services of various types.

Consequently, this is where the globalization and internationalization of the legal sphere come from. Lawyers and advocates from different countries have the opportunity to speak the same language, discussing mutual interests and cooperation. Therefore, the globalization of the legal sphere at present requires a lawyer who, along with deep knowledge in his professional sphere, has a certain level of English proficiency. These factors will create a favorable environment for communication with foreign colleagues and participation in discussing various professional topics in English. Expressing personal ideas and thoughts during consultations with foreign individuals and legal entities is another advantage of learning a language.

It should be pointed out that one of the significant factors of knowledge of legal English is its importance in taking part in negotiations. Cooperation with foreign firms requires deep understanding of particular words and terminology alongside commonly spoken language, with good communication skills. Indeed, one can address dictionaries directly or ask for help from experienced colleagues working with documentation. But during negotiations, thinking quickly and voice all the necessary information without delay is strongly required.

One of the crucial roles of the meaning of the English legal language is the opportunity to participate in international conferences. It is generally known that such events are held mainly in the "world" language, English. The significance of this

fact is that participating in such events certainly improves a specialist's qualifications, along with which the level of a lawyer in the labor market rises.

Foreign languages also provide an excellent opportunity to understand specific features connected to culture and ideology closely related to foreign legislation. At the same time, knowing English, it will not be difficult to understand the essence of many laws and regulations of English and American legislation.

Taking everything into consideration, it can be concluded that the globalization of the legal profession in the modern world is an urgent need. Lawyers who know English have a better chance of success in this field. Linguistic literacy is now an integral factor in a modern lawyer's career and personal growth.

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